

Dividend Relevance and the Value of Firms in Nigeria

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Abstract

The COVID-19 period made investors to become rational in their decisions as well as allowing them to see the relevance of dividend when firms operate optimally. This research aims to analyse the relevance of dividend payments in the value of the firm. Using panel data for 15 firms listed by the Nigerian Exchange Limited and covering the years 2012 to 2021 with the employment of the Generalised Linear Model and the relevance theory of dividend, the study reviewed that dividend per share and retained earnings significantly influenced the value of the firm. The study reconfirms the relevance of dividend and the value of the firm using Tobin Q. However, dividend yield was found not to be statistically significant to the value of the firm. From the findings, the study recommends that policy makers should ensure that priority is given to selected variables such as dividend per share as their impact strongly affects the value of the firm.

Keywords: Tobin Q, Dividend, Value of firm, Regression, Nigerian Exchange Limited

Introduction

Income is the net amount that occurs between the earnings that businesses have attained at the conclusion of their reporting year and the expenses incurred to generate those revenues. Firms exist primarily to generate profits. Maximising a company's market worth or increasing the wealth of its owners is the primary the goal of corporate management. Financing, investing, and dividend policies make up the three fundamental corporate managerial strategies. Dividend is then defined as the transfer of a portion of the profit made by the firms to the owners or partnerships at the conclusion of the reporting duration, particularly when the researchers discuss dividend distribution or dividend policies. The dividend allocation strategy is therefore crucial for publicly traded firms whose shares are listed on the stock exchange. A dividend practice is implemented to compensate investors or increase corporate worth. One of the very essential managerial finance choices is dividend policy. With the help of the firm's dividend procedures, dividend is determined when and how much of the period's profits will be distributed, and it is made clear if this will have an impact on the firm's value. According to Awen, et al. (2022), neither the firm's worth nor decisions about dividends have any bearing on the capital structure. However, in Munzhelele et al. (2022) viewpoints, the researchers discovered that dividend payout decisions impact the company's valuation. According to Bossman et al. (2022) supporting this idea, dividends have a significant impact on share value, and share pricing also has a significant impact on dividends.

The rise of the number of banks in Nigeria after the Coronavirus pandemic indicates that banking business is profitable. However, the distribution of profit in form of dividend by non-servicing firms in Nigeria nosedives as a result of unpalatable financial and economic activities caused by COVID-19 (Olawajaju & Ajeyalemi, 2023). As most firms in other sectors in Nigeria began to recover from the shock of COVID-19, most analysts believe that dividend is relevant in any economic situation.

In most companies' perspective, payment of dividend is dependent on selecting an appropriate dividend policy which is significant decision for most firms operating in the stock market. Also, in services business, the flexibility of investors coming with suggestions for firms to invest in projects

with potential cash flows is essential. This is because the dividends received by shareholders are dependent on cash flows and profit made by the firm. Kadir et al. (2022), stated the features of firms that pays dividend in the Malaysia dividend streams and found out that even firms that pay dividend are not strong in profitability generations but they are less risky due to economic stability and government supports for business growth. These factors makes firms in Malaysia survive as compared to other firms in other less developed countries that does not pay dividend.

Dividend policy emphasises two ideas as stated by some scholars, the first is the amount paid and the second is the amount retained but most scholars only consider the amount paid as dividend. Justifiable reasons irrespective of the amount retained or paid is that the total funds still belong to the shareholders (Akinsanya, 2022; Khan, 2022). In spite of ever increasing focus on the dividend policy, as at present, no definition can be pick-pointed as universally accepted conclusion as regards dividend policy and payment because of the enormous discussions of mixed results that expresses various views concerning dividend policy. This has made it difficult and conveys a decision that the harder we look, the difficulty we see to conclude, because it is like a puzzle with piece that don't fit together". Biswas et al. (2022) describes the research on dividend as a research rated and one of the top ten difficult areas of research in finance because it provided an unsolved solution for decades.

A major conflict is to appropriately answer the question on dividend policy influence on the market price of firms. To question the extent of dividend payment and the value of firms most times in finance, the value of a firm is measured by the price of the firm. However, two schools of thought debate this question and they include the school of thought that represents the view that dividend policy affect the value of the firm through the share price (Gbenga & Ayobami, 2022; Koleosho et al., 2022), while the second school of thought holistically stated that the history of dividend policy and its future debates would bear no relevance as far as the business firm market value is put into consideration (Fayyaz et al., 2023). The two schools of thought have been in existence for long and researchers align themselves to any of the school of thought with support focusing on the linear link that was noted to exist in connection with dividend policy and share price is just an attempt made to corroborate the disapproval of the stated hypothesis.

Most times the firm value is represented by the share value or by the report as stated on the market capitalization of the firm. It has been proven that the only benefits of the company as regards dividend is that all decisions are point down to the firm's investment decisions made at any point in time. Psarommatis and Kiritsis (2022) stated that managers are expected to incorporate the issue of the amount needed as earnings and also the amount needed as share price when taking decisions as both factors are significant in the growth of the firm. Rahman (2022) stated that the study of fall in share price is absolutely in line with the decline in the payment of dividend while a pronouncement of dividend; increase the perception of a rise in the price of shares. In Nigeria, severe expansion was experienced in the era of indigenisation, COVID-19 and the storm of global crisis affected the country. Such negative effects brought about a nosedive in the market value of the equity shares of listed firms itemized in the capital market according to Adeogun (2022). This project examined data from pre and post COVID-19 era on dividend and stock price on firms listed on the capital market in Nigeria.

Ain et al. (2021) stated that managers that pay dividend are regarded as strong while weak mangers don't pay dividend. This is an interesting problem because shareholders considered the payment of dividend as a parameter for return of investment, hard work of managers and the progress of the firm because investors gain confidence on firms that pay dividend. Researchers such as Septiani et al. (2020) and Husna and Satria (2019) are of the opinion that the financial strength of a firm is not measured by the amount of profit generated or the amount paid by dividend as it is assumed by others. Therefore, this study examined the various needs of shareholders through proxies of variables to examine the effect of dividend on value, admitting the problem that firm manager's uses policy to pays dividend are strong and firms that uses policy not to pay dividend are weak. The aim of the study

is to examine the extent in which dividend payment and the retained earnings ratio affect the value of the firms listed on Nigerian Exchange Limited.

The study will also assist investors in making their investment decisions as well as aiding to expose the various factors that may influence the value of the firm and the dividend payment. The study have been arranged to provide solid information for researchers that are new in this field and also to serve as rich materials for future finance researchers and investors. Similarly, this research is to add value to the existing body of knowledge.

Literature review

The traditional school alternatively called the dividend relevance was regarded as a school popularly called the rightist. This means that researchers in this school of thought discussed the issue of dividend relevance payment to shareholders (Asquith & Mullins, 1983). According to them, the assessment of the dividend's effect on stock price was found to be longer-lasting and more significant than the effect on the amount of money reabsorbed by businesses. The consequence is that dividends should be paid consideration since they have a greater impact on share prices than the company's retained profits. These assertions were later discussed by Triani and Tarmidi (2019). Similarly, Greenhalgh and Campani (2023) gave an expressive and detailed explanation to support the relevance of dividend payment.

Bar-Yosef and Kolodny (1976) stated that dichotomy between the dividend importance and the dividend irrelevance schools as noted by other scholars affirmed that the result of the number of persons that support the schools varies. If the proportion of persons is equal, the argument continues but if the support tend towards the right or left, one of the schools would have seize to exist. However, Riaz et al. (2020) concluded that dividend are more relevant when the market is slow than when the market is fast as investors have information in the market to take any decision that best suit them. Fons et al. (2021) looked at intelligent view in the short and long run analysis of investment stock return and concluded that the market is dynamic and thus react to the forces and demand across industry. The researchers concluded that dividend policy affecting the value of the firm is based on information obtained by managers prior to the knowledge of shareholders as regards market operations.

Ayunku and Apiri (2020) were of the opinion that dividend affect prices in a regulated market. Earnings per share and dividend yield (DY), also known as dividend pay-out ratio, serve as supporting variables when analysing dividend policy and net asset per share in a regulated market. It was observed that the dependent variable was noted to be market price share while others were regarded as independent variables. The information used are all collected from the financial statements of 10 firms operating in consumer goods and are quoted in Nigerian stock market within the period of 2004 to 2018. The study findings support the claims that dividend affect the value of firms in as much as the market in which the firm operates is regulated. The investigation of Anaeto et al. (2021) established that dividend policy affect the value of the firm by using Pakistan market between the year 2006-2015. A total of 51 firms were used in the study to examine dividend policy and share prices in the Pakistan stock market. Secondary data are stationed for time series and corroborates with the study objectives. Auto distributive lad and the birds in hand theory were used in the study. The result of the study shows that dividend yield has a positive and substantial effect on share prices. Also earnings yield and dividend payout ratios were accounted to negatively affect share prices. It was noted that the analysis and review done corroborates that the use of dividend in corporate business align with the important of dividend and share price increase. Anaeto et al. (2021) supported the findings of Iqbal et al. (2022). The focus of the study was on determinants of dividend policy of petroleum firms in Nigeria. The period under investigation was within the year 2011-2014. Fifteen oil and gas firms were selected from the oil and gas sector in Nigeria as they are listed. The data were extracted from the financial statements and a panel data were formed. Simple statistic and co-integration methods and test of stationarity were used as methods of analysis. The result signifies that

there is a positive link between the dividend payout and shareholders wealth creation among the firms in the oil sector. Cyril et al. (2020), measured the link among dividend policy and financial performance of oil and gas companies in Nigeria using data extracted from the year 2005 and 2014. The results corroborates with the results of Anaeto et al. (2021).

Louziri and Oubal (2022) supported the assertion that dividend policies affect the value of the firm by assessing effects earnings on stock price in Morocco. Firms financial statement were used and grouped based on behaviour of the share prices using a range of firms paying high or low dividend across a particular period. The data comprises of stock prices, dividend, the retained earnings and general earning after tax to the dividend paid per share. Pooled least square regression model and both fixed and random effect analysis was used. The Hausman test was also adopted and the general findings showed that current dividend has a significant positive effect on the stock prices. Also earnings and recoded previous dividend were regarded as payments that insignificantly affected banks' stock prices. Gbenga and Ayobami (2022), look deeply on testing the application of the Miller and Modigliani dividend policy irrelevant hypothesis in Nigeria stock market. The validity was tested with the Tobin Q hypothesis to checkmates the occurrence of dividend irrelevant among businesses. Variables used by the researcher include dividend payout ratio, retention ratio, per share of dividend paid and the dividend yield. 20 firms were used and the information obtained was selected based on criteria needed to obtain a valid answer to the research questions. The study was set to be for 10 years with the period of 2008-2017. The study finding shows that dividend affects the value of the market based on some premise that the trade-off between dividend payout and retain earnings are effectively managed. Also the proportion of retained earnings and dividend paid support the knowledge that investor have on dividend policy.

Idewele and Murad (2019) stated that dichotomy between the dividend relevance and the dividend irrelevance schools is as a result of the number of persons that support the schools. If the proportion of persons is equal, the argument continues but if the support tends towards the right or left, one of the schools would have seizes to exist. Simshauser (2023) concluded that dividend are more relevant when the market is slows than when the market is fast as investors have information in the market to take any decision that best suit them. Idewele and Murad (2019) looked at intelligent view in the short and long run analyses of investment stuck return and concluded that the market is dynamic and thus react to the forces and demand across industry. He concluded that dividend policy affecting the value of the firm is based on information obtained by managers prior to the knowledge of shareholders as regard market operations.

Ojogbo et al. (2022) was of the opinion that dividend affect stock price and the value of the firm. He used dividend yield (DY), dividend pay-out ratio, and earnings per share as support variables to examine dividend policy and net asset per share (NAPS). It was observed that the dependent variable was noted to be market price share while others were regarded as independent variables. All data were sourced from the financial statements of different firms operating in consumer goods and are quoted in Nigerian stock market. The studies' findings support the claims that dividend affect the value of firms. However, Idewele and Murad (2019) supported other literature that investigated the effect of dividend policies and cooperate performance using firms listed in the Nigeria market and concluded that dividend affect profit. Oniyama et al. (2021) also supported that dividend affects profit through their analysis carried in the United Kingdom (UK) using retail industries. Udoka et al. (2022), stated that following the trend of report of firms listed on Nigerian stock exchange concerning dividend payment, is a valid source to practically analyse if dividend payment is relevant or not across firms.

Conceptual model

Figure 1: The conceptual model
 Source: Developed by researchers, 2023

Methodology

Generalised Linear Model (GLM) was adopted as the methodology of the study. However, the descriptive statistics and Correlation were used as estimation techniques. With the study focus to find the effect of dividend payment on the value of the firm in Nigeria, the ex post facto research design was adopted to mathematically formulate the model that would best fit the study. By this design, the researchers were convinced that the result of the study would be rich and thus led to significant recommendations in practice. The population for this research was 40 listed firms. These firms comprises of both financial and non-financial firms. The rationale for choosing these firms as population was based on the availability of their financial statement up to the year 2021.

A convenience research sampling was adopted as sampling technique. For reliability and justification of the population of this study, access to information within the scope of the study was used as the selection criteria to pick samples from the population of 40 listed firms for the study. Also the financial statements that are in public domain by the listed firms from 2012 to 2021 are regarded as consideration factors. Based on the convenience sampling techniques, the researchers focused on 15 firms due to the availability of data on public domain. To ensure that data are accurate, the researchers expanded the periods to 10 years study. Hence the total observations expected in the study are 150 observations. Panel secondary data were collected from Mecharatios Limited and Sigma Securities. The models specifications are modeled in line with the study focus and the work of Badagaga (2017).

$$TQ_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1DPS_{it} + \beta_2DY_{it} + \beta_3RE_{it} + \mu_{it} \dots \dots \dots \text{General Model}$$

Where:

- TQ - The Value of the Firm
- DPS - The Dividend per Share
- RE - The Retained Earnings Ratio
- DY - The Dividend Yield
- β_0 - The Slope of the regression
- $\beta_{1,2,3}$ - Coefficient of the variables
- μ - Error term

Table 1: Descriptive statistics

	TQ	RE	DY	DPS
Mean	40.50000	0.389000	0.229000	0.229000
Median	42.02000	0.360000	0.761900	0.761900
Maximum	42.30000	0.790000	0.512010	0.512010
Minimum	37.90000	0.120000	0.460000	0.460000
Std. Dev.	0.614403	0.193491	0.108121	0.108121
Skewness	0.582634	0.474898	0.137128	0.137128
Kurtosis	3.193537	2.592497	1.326497	1.326497
Jarque-Bera	2.334441	1.126781	0.136711	0.136711
Probability	0.000000	0.003836	0.440172	0.440172
Sum	58.72500	97.25000	13.63100	13.63100
Sum Sq. Dev.	13.19525	9.322250	7.012034	7.012034
Observations	150	150	150	150

Source: EView9, 2022.

Figure 1: CUSUM

Table 2: Correlation results

	TQ	RE	DY	DPS
TQ	1.000000	-0.002566	0.356044	-0.005687
RE	-0.002566	1.000000	0.089620	-0.437558
DY	0.356044	0.089620	1.000000	-0.456643
DPS	-0.005687	-0.437558	-0.456643	1.000000

Source: Eview9, 2022.

From the table above, we could see that both positive and negative correlation among the variables proxy for firm values and dividend payments.

The variables comprised of 150 observations which are 15 firms with financial data for 10 years 2012-2021. The average value estimated for TQ was valued to be 40.5. The highest and lowest point in which TQ value can range is 42.3 and 39.7 respectively. The result shows that the market value increases to 42.3 and falls to 39.7 on the average.

$$TQ_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DPS_{it} + \beta_2 DY_{it} + \beta_3 RE_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

Table 3: Regression results

Dependent Variable: TQ
 Method: Generalized Linear Model (Newton-Raphson / Marquardt steps)
 Date: 01/19/23 Time: 18:52
 Sample: 2012 2021
 Included observations: 150
 Family: Normal
 Link: Identity
 Dispersion computed using Pearson Chi-Square
 Convergence achieved after 1 iteration
 Coefficient covariance computed using observed Hessian

Variable	Coefficien t	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.156618	0.070010	-2.237091	0.0253
DPS	0.134530	0.013573	9.911750	0.0000
DY	0.017517	0.005851	2.993638	0.0028
RE	0.134228	0.019577	6.856502	0.0000
Mean dependent var	0.362727	S.D. dependent var		0.202609
Sum squared resid	2.211750	Log likelihood		121.5520
Akaike info criterion	-1.388510	Schwarz criterion		-1.256742
Hannan-Quinn criter.	-1.335021	Deviance		2.211750
Deviance statistic	0.013998	Restr. Deviance		6.732273
LR statistic	322.9309	Prob(LR statistic)		0.000000
Pearson SSR	2.211750	Pearson statistic		0.013998
Dispersion	0.013998			

Source: Eview9, 2022

Discussions of results

This study corroborates with the work of Mishra and Mishra (2020), that dividend yield (DY) nosedive the market share price of firms which operates in a regulated market. The mathematical value links of MPS is -0.01176. This represents a negative link coupled with a coefficient of determination of 75%. The hypothesis of model one confirms that dividend yield of quoted firms does not affects the share prices. However, the work of Arsal (2021) and Ayunku and Timipere (2020), justify that the use of dividend yield may not affects shares prices of firms. The researchers affirmed the reasons behind the needs for yield to have a strong effect on stock price volatility by using 73 selected firms that are traded in a regulated market channel by Karachi Stock Exchange (KSE-100). These analysis was put together and they affirmed that the slight difference why yield is regarded as proportionately important is that there is a negate variance on dividend yield. This study also support the work of Douglas (2022) as regard the effect of dividend yield on share price.

Retained earnings ratio value was noted in the study result to be -1.908643. This indicates a nosedive of value on market shares. The prices of quoted firms and the statistical test affirmed that in as much as there is the existence of a nosedive in the value of the quoted firms, the retained earnings is considered as a value that is not proportionately significant in affecting the market prices of the quoted firms' shares. Abubakar (2020) supported others results regarding retained earnings ratio on firms' value. They stated that if there exists a high retained earnings ratio proportionately higher than expected, there is tendency for prices of shares to perform well in crisis period.

The implication of the value is that it connotes a decline. The R^2 shows that 47% of market price shares of quoted firms are captured by the value of the firm (TQ). Kayode & Olaolu, (2020) stated the up and down movement of the stock price path posit a strong evidence that earnings and dividend per share would be affected by the fluctuations in stock price. Their explanation was that most times, the payment of earnings is dependent on the value of the firm. They further explained that earnings can be classified into three degree. However, Mohamed et al. (2021) supported the work of Kayode and Olaolu (2020) by concluding that earnings per share are calculated for the aim of distributing profit for investors hence earnings per share is a quantum of the share price. Noting the implication of earnings per share on market price per share, studies like Qiu et al. (2021) defend the significant effect of earnings per share on the market price per share as well as the overall value of the firm. To generalise this connection, this study therefore shows empirically that the link between DPS and TQ is negative in quoted firms in the Nigeria Stock Exchange market. Also the relationship between dividend yield (DY) and retained earnings (RE) in this study is negative and DY does not affect TQ.

Conclusion

The study became essential when dividend payment became an action of predicting the value of the firm's in Nigeria after the COVID-19. However, many literature stated that predicting the value of

the firm accurately is difficult because of the up and downs (fluctuations) of share prices in the capital market. Also the uncertainty in the Nigerian economy contributes more difficulties in predicting price and the value of the firm. In conclusion, the study supports other literature that underpinned the significance of paying dividend by firms in operating in a regulated market. Therefore the theories of dividend are used as supports in this study to provide the base and the empirical analysis that dividend payment are integral of the value of the firm. This study has examined the impact of dividend payment and the value of the firms in Nigeria. It was found out that dividend payment affects the value of the firms. On the stated premise of the study that the established findings answer the research questions and statistically affirmed the hypotheses stated. It was observed that in as much as the payment of dividend is regarded as vital in today's economy, there is positive link that also exist between earnings per share and the value of the firm operating in a regulated market in Nigeria. The negative relationship that exists between Dividend Yield (DY) and TQ was pointed to the statistical interpretation of a negative coefficient attached to DY that would necessitate a fall in TQ. Therefore, this work absolutely support and contribute to the work of Monteiro et al. (2020) and Oji and Nwosi (2021).

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